

Plant for Utilization of Organoplastic Bodies of Solid-Propellant Rockets

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Abstract – In this article, there are the elaborated scheme of the plant for ecological friendly utilization of organoplastic bodies of solid-propellant rockets and description of the principle of plant's action. The article contains the results of experimental investigations on development of technological parameters of low-temperature pyrolysis of organoplastic with production of liquid alternative fuel.

Keywords – cracking, liquid artificial fuel, low-temperature pyrolysis, organoplastic

INTRODUCTION

INTERNATIONAL cooperation in the sphere of armament has led to signing the agreements of limitation and destruction of strategic weapons including the rockets with solid-propellant rocket engines (SPRE).

At present, Ukraine has a status of a nuclear-free state. Now there is a necessity of solving a problem of utilization of space rocketry at sharply increased level of its destruction.

One of basic components of utilized rockets with SPRE is their body which consists of organoplastic and rubber and which should be utilized with minimization of costs and with provision of ecological safety.

Yuzhnoye State Design Office (YSDO) and Nikolayev Shipbuilding University (NSU) named after admiral Makarov have developed a technology and elaborated a plant for low-temperature pyrolysis of blocks of SPRE bodies with production of alternative liquid fuel at financial support of the project by Science and Technology Centre in Ukraine (STCU). A scheme of the plant is given in Fig. 1.

The technological cycle is carried out in the following way. A polymeric block 2 (PB) is loaded into reactor 1 which is equipped with an electric heater. The reactor is a unit with the internal diameter from 2.5 up to 2.6 m and

the height of a cylindrical part from 6.0 up to 6.5 m. The reactor is made in such a way that the whole polymeric block is placed inside that cylindrical part.

There is a cover in the upper part of the reactor; that cover can be easily removed. Sealing of the joint of the cover and the body is performed using a principle of liquid seal; alloys on the basis of lead and bismuth are used as stopping liquid. It was determined by experiments that operational temperature of the reactor is from plus 580 up to plus 600°C, estimated pressure is 5 kPa (500 mm of water column). Installed capacity of the electric heater is about 130 kW.

Filling the volume of the system by inert gas provides safety of the technological process; that filling is carried out from the inert gas generator 37.

Preliminary heating of the polymeric block is performed due to thermal energy accumulated during the previous technological cycle; it leads to 40–60% reduction of energy consumption for PB processing. This phase is fulfilled in the following way. Thermal accumulating material (TAM) which is alloy on the basis of lead-bismuth, is pumped through TAM heat exchanger 28 from tank 25 of hot TAM by a pump of hot TAM through a valve. Then it goes through a valve of cold TAM to tank 22 of cold TAM. TAM heat exchanger 28 is pumped by ventilator 36 by inert gas from the reactor through the cyclone steam separator 35.

PB heating and thermal processing are carried out in the reactor due to heat supply from the electric heater 3. Decomposition products in the gas phase are supplied to the cracking reactor 5 of hydrocarbons and further to the dephlegmator 7 which is cooled by air. It provides their additional processing for production of liquid fuel components in the condenser 9. Mixture of liquid and gaseous decomposition products is supplied to the tank-separator 14; liquid fraction is supplied by the fuel pump 15 from the tank-separator to the diesel generator 13 which provides power for the whole technological process. Gaseous decomposition products are supplied from the tank-separator 14 to the cleaning system 38, 39, 40, and further to the inlet collector of the diesel generator 13. Triple cleaning system provides separation of hydrocarbon gas from deleterious impurities.

After completion of PB thermal processing, we carry out the expulsion of gaseous products of the reaction from the system by inert gas through the additional condenser 19, cooling of that condenser is performed by a water

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Fig. 1 – Scheme of Cyclic Operation Plant.

system which includes the circulation pump 18, the air cooling unit 17 with the axial ventilator 16. Mixture of liquid and gaseous decomposition products is supplied to the tank-separator 20. Liquid fraction from the tank-separator is supplied by pump 21 to the cracking reactor 5 of hydrocarbons; additional thermal processing of those hydrocarbons takes place in the cracking reactor. Gaseous decomposition products from the tank-separator 20 are supplied to the cleaning system and further to the inlet collector of the diesel generator.

Energy balance and alternative fuel production and consumption are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
ENERGY CONSUMPTION OR INCOME

#	Energy consumption or income	Data
1	Heat energy for pyrolysis reactor pre-heating till decomposition temperature, $\times 10^6$ J	from 1470 up to 1840
2	Heat energy for pyrolysis reactor heating till decomposition temperature, $\times 10^6$ J	2880
3	Heat energy for pyrolysis reactor heating from heat storage accumulator, $\times 10^6$ J	from 1040 up to 1410
4	Required heat energy for decomposition, $\times 10^6$ J	691

5	Heat energy for cracking reactor heating, $\times 10^6$ J	1440
6	Total energy consumption for technological process, $\times 10^6$ J	from 3600 up to 3960
7	Amount of produced alternative fuel, kg	390
8	Specific fuel consumption for electricity production, 10^{-6} kg/J	0,07
9	Fuel consumption for technological process (without heat storage and recuperation), kg	from 250 up to 275
10	Amount of the trade alternative fuel, kg	from 115 up to 140

The results of experimental researches allowed to approve the efficiency and ecological safety of the proposed technology. Amount of the alternative diesel fuel, produced in utilization process is enough not for aramide blocks decomposition only, and a significant amount of this fuel can be supplied for customers as trade product. Sanitary investigations have shown that the content of the most hazardous substances is not more than 30% from the Sanitary Rules limit level.

Definition of the initial data for design of the aramide polymer blocks (SPRE) utilization unit is impossible without identification of the technological process parameters. Pyrolysis temperature of the aramide composite influence onto not-condensing gases'

production is extremely important. These gases can not be transformed into liquid artificial fuel and therefore their production should be maximally limited.

Fig. 2 presents dependence of the not-condensing gases' production upon the pyrolysis temperature.

1, 2, 3, 4, 5 – numbers of experiments; 6 – dependence of the not-condensing gases' production upon the pyrolysis temperature.

Fig.2 - Investigation of the influence of not-condensing gases' production upon the pyrolysis temperature.

Minimal production of the not-condensing gases occurs at a temperature of 825K; these gases comprise around 0.025 (2.5%) at the stated temperature. Important to note that at this temperature aramide polymer is not undergoing complete decomposition and total production of the useful hydrocarbons is very small. Previous experiments showed that the most rational pyrolysis temperature ranges between 850 to 875K, at which not-condensing gases production comprise from 0.05 up to 0.075 (from 5 up to 7.5%), which is an acceptable level for such process. When the pyrolysis temperature is increased, not-condensing gases' production dramatically increases (from 0.15 up to 0.18 or from 15 up to 18%) and becomes less controllable which indicates inconsistency of the experimental data; this is shown in Fig. 2.

Caloric capacity Q_{hp}^g , density ρ_g , and cracking gases' production $G(T_d)$ upon pyrolysis temperature T_p and temperature in the dephlegmator T_d , were thoroughly investigated. Results of these studies are presented in Fig. 3.

It was determined that cracking process temperatures have certain impact onto caloric capacity of the gases that are obtained during aramide polymer cracking. For instance, at a temperature of 800K, caloric capacity Q_{hp}^g equals to 48 MJ/kg and at a temperature 900K this number increases up to 48,4 MJ/kg, what is explained by increased depth of the polymer material decomposition and increased hydrogen production, which has higher caloric capacity.

Fig.3 - Dependence of caloric capacity, density, cracking gases' production upon pyrolysis temperature.

Dependence of the gases density upon cracking process temperatures was determined. For instance, at a temperature of 800K density of these gases equals to 3.25 kg/m³, and at a temperature of 900K this number decreases to 1.15 kg/m³; this can be explained by increased depth of the polymer material decomposition and production of the lighter gaseous substances.

Dependence of the total production of the liquid cracking products upon temperature of the heat transferring surface of the dephlegmator was determined as well. For instance, at a cracking temperature of 440K production of such gases $G(T_d)$ comprises 0.4 kg, whereas at a temperature of 900K their production comprises 3.05 kg.

Fractional composition of the not-condensing gases that result in a cracking process is extremely important. Qualitative and quantitative data of not-condensing gases was obtained after a series of experimental studies and presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 - Fraction content of non-condensed gases at different pyrolysis temperature.

Presented data allow following conclusions that at a lower pyrolysis temperatures (800K), predominant fractions of not-condensing gases are the ones that contain following number of carbons: C5, C4, and C3 (listed in descending order). Such gases are pentanes

(n-pentane, neopentane, cyclopentane, etc.), propanes (2-methylpropane, methylpropane, cyclobutane, etc.), and butanes (buten, butylene, propylene, etc.). Hydrocarbons, which are found in the mixture, are present in lower quantities. Contrary, at a temperature of 900K, predominant fractions of hydrocarbons present in the mixture are the ones containing C1 and C2, whereas hydrocarbons containing C5, C4, and C3 are presented in much lower quantities.

Hydrogen presence in the mixture of pyrolysis gases should not be neglected when selecting reactors' materials and other elements that are present in the hydrogen environment. Hydrogen corrosion may be represented by the following reaction

when carbon present in the alloy interacts with hydrogen present in the gaseous mixture, methane synthesis takes place. This methane has much higher volume and has a capacity to destroy the substance from inside (hydrogen corrosion or hydrogen fragility). In this case one has to select materials that are not inclined to hydrogen corrosion. Steels and steel mixtures with lower carbon content and higher nickel content are such materials.

Technological parameters of the processes which carry out in the units of the plant have been experimentally determined by the Project participants. Structural parameters of the units have been estimated. The Project has been successfully completed by issue of Technical Project of the plant.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Science and Technology Center in Ukraine (STCU) for financial support to carry out this research and experimental work. We would also like to thank Prof. Nickolas J. Themelis, Director of the Earth Engineering Centre of Columbia University and Prof. Marco J. Castaldi from Department of Earth and Environmental Engineering this University, NYC, USA for their extremely valuable discussions regarding plastic waste processing.

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